

Ba'zi Klassik Muammolar Va Taqsimotlar

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada Ba'zi muhim taqsimotlar (Bernulli, Binomial, Puasson Tekis, Normal, ko'rsatkichli) asosan Binomial taqsimot, Vandermond taqsimot va Nyorlund taqsimotlari keltirilgan yuzasida masalalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ba'zi muhim taqsimotlar (Bernulli, Binomial taqsimot, Vandermond taqsimot va Nyorlund taqsimotlari)

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№ 1. Quyidagilarni ko'rsating

$$(a) (x + y)^n = \sum_{k=0}^n C_n^k x^k y^{n-k} \quad (\text{Binomial taqsimot}),$$

$$(b) (x + y)_n = \sum_{k=0}^n C_n^k (x)_k (y)_{n-k} \quad (\text{Vandermond taqsimot}),$$

$$(c) x^{\underline{n}} + y^{\underline{n}} = \sum_{k=0}^n C_n^k x^{\underline{k}} y^{\underline{n-k}} \quad (\text{Nyorlund taqsimot}),$$

bu yerda

$$(x)_n = x(x-1)(x-2)\dots(x-n+1),$$

$$x^{\underline{n}} = (x+1)(x+2)\dots(x+n-1).$$

Yechim. (a) Agar $(x + y)^n$ ichidagi barcha qavslarni o'xshash hadlarni qatnashtirmasdan ochsak, $x^k y^{n-k}, k = 0, \dots, n$. ko'rinishdagi 2^n ta hadga ega bo'lamiz. Agar $x^k y^{n-k}$ ichidagi k ta qavsdan x hadni, qolganlaridan y ni olsak, $(x + y)^n$ hadi olinadi. $(x + y)^n$ ichida aynan k ta qavs C_n^k usullarida tanlanishi mumkin, ya'ni $(x + y)^n$ da qavslarni ochishda $x^k y^{n-k}$ lar soni bir xil bo'ladi.

(b) X to'planning elementlaridan farqli $x, y \in N, x \leq n, y \leq n$. bo'lsin, x farqli elementlardan iborat X to'plam va y elementlardan iborat Y to'plamlar ko'rib chiqilsin. $X \cap Y$ uzunligi n dan tartiblangan to'plam elementlari soni. Bir tomondan, bu n bo'ylab $x + y$ ning

¹ [[1]-73-93-betlarni qarang]

tartibga solish soni. Boshqa tomondan, barcha to'plamlarni ulardagi X elementlar soniga ko'ra sinflarga bo'lish mumkin, bu elementlarning sonini k deb belgilaydi. Uzunligi k bo'lgan X tartiblangan elementlar to'plami soni $(x)_k$, Y dan $n - k$ uzunlik $(y)_{n-k}$ ga teng. X elementlar va Y elementlar o'rtasida tartibni saqlagan holda bu to'plamlarni aralashtirish usullari soni C_n^k . Shunday qilib, har bir sinfdagi to'plamlar soni $C_n^k x_k y_{n-k}$ bo'lib, bu $x, y \in N, x \leq n, y \leq n$ uchun kerakli formulani isbotlaydi.

Agar $x, y \in R$ bo'lsa, biz Vandermonde taqsimotining chap va o'ng tomonlari x va y ko'phadlari ekanligini topamiz, ularning qiymatlari sanab o'tiladigan nuqtalar soniga to'g'ri keladi. Bu shuni anglatadiki, ko'phadlar bir xil tengdir.

(c) Agar qarama-qarshi belgi bilan x va y ni olsak va quyidagi

$$(-x)_n = \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k C_n^k x^k$$

dan, Norlundning o'ziga xosligi Vandermonde taqsimotidan kelib chiqadi.

№ 2. Ehtimoliy, kombinatoriyal, geometrik mulohazalardan foydalanish (masalan, qulay imkoniyatlar sonini yoki bir nuqtadan ikkinchisiga olib boradigan yo'llar sonini turli yo'llar bilan hisoblash) va boshqa mulohazalar (aytaylik, algebraik, masalan, x^n uchun koeffitsientlarni hisoblash va taqqoslashda va quyidagi tenglikda

$$(1+x)^a (1+x)^b = (1+x)^{a+b},$$

Binomial koeffitsientlarning quyidagi xossalarini qaraymiz:²

$$1 = C_n^0 < C_n^1 < \dots < C_n^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} = C_n^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} > \dots > C_n^{n-1} > C_n^n = 1$$

(bu yerda simmetriya va unimodallik xosasi

$$C_n^k = \max \{n \hat{=} Z : n \geq x\}, \quad C_n^k = \min \{n \hat{=} Z : n \geq x\},$$

$$2. \quad C_n^{k-1} + C_n^k = C_{n+1}^k \text{ - "Paskal uchburchagi", "Paskal taqsimoti"},$$

$$3. \quad C_n^k = C_{n-2}^k + 2C_{n-2}^{k-1} + C_{n-2}^{k-2},$$

$$4. \quad \sum_{k=0}^n C_n^k = 2^n,$$

$$5. \quad \sum_{k=0}^n (C_n^k)^2 = C_{2n}^n,$$

$$6. \quad \sum_{k=0}^n 2^k C_n^k = 3^n,$$

$$7. \quad \sum_{k=1}^n k C_n^k = n 2^{n-1},$$

² [[3]-123-144-betlarni qarang] binomial taqsimot xossalari keltirilgan.

$$8. \sum_{m=0}^k (-1)^{k-m} C_n^m = C_{n-1}^k, \quad n \geq k+1,$$

$$9. \sum_{k=0}^n k(k-1)C_n^k = n(n-1)2^{n-2}, \quad n \geq 2,$$

$$10. kC_n^k = nC_{n-1}^{k-1},$$

$$11. \sum_{m=k}^n C_m^k = C_{n+1}^{k+1},$$

$$12. C_n^m C_m^k = C_n^k C_{n-k}^{m-k}, \quad k \leq m \leq n,$$

$$13. \sum_{m=0}^k C_{n+m}^m = C_{n+k+1}^k,$$

$$14. \sum_{m=0}^k C_{n+1}^m = \sum_{m=0}^k 2^m C_{n-m}^{k-m}, \quad k \leq n,$$

$$(a^*) C_{n-k}^k + C_{n-k-1}^{k-1} = \frac{n}{n-k} C_{n-k}^k, \quad k \leq n,$$

$$(b^*) C_{n_1-n_2}^n = \sum_{k=0}^{n_1} C_{n_1}^k C_{n_2}^{n-k} \text{ -Vandermonde binomial taqsimoti,}$$

$$(c^*) C_n^{k-1} C_n^{k+1} \leq (C_n^k)^2, \quad k \leq n-1,$$

$$(d^*) C_{m+n}^n \leq \frac{n!}{m!} + \frac{m!}{n!} + \frac{n!}{m!}, \text{ yoki ekvivalent } \frac{(m+n)!}{(m+n)^{m+n}} \leq \frac{m!n!}{m^m n^n},$$

$$(e^*) \frac{n^k}{k^k} \leq C_n^k \leq \frac{n^k}{k!},$$

$$(f^*) \sum_{k=0}^n C_n^k (-1)^{n-k} 2^k = 1,$$

$$(g^*) C_n^k = \sum_{m=k}^n (-1)^{n-m} C_n^m C_m^k 2^{m-k}, \quad 1 \leq k \leq n,$$

$$(h^*) \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k (C_n^k)^2 = \begin{cases} (-1)^m \frac{(2m)!}{(m!)^2}, & \text{agar } n = 2m \\ 0, & \text{aks holda} \end{cases}$$

$$(i^*) \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k (C_n^k)^3 = \begin{cases} (-1)^m \frac{(3m)!}{(m!)^3}, & \text{agar } n = 2m \\ 0, & \text{aks holda} \end{cases} \text{ -Dikson ayniyat}$$

$$(j^*) \sum_{k=1}^n \binom{n}{k} \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k},$$

$$(k^*) \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{n-k} k^m \binom{n}{k} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{agar } m < n, \\ n!, & \text{agar } m = n, \end{cases}$$

$$(l^*) \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n-k}{2(n-k)} \binom{k}{2k} = 2^{2n},$$

$$(m^*) \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} \binom{k}{n} \binom{k}{m} \frac{1}{m} = \frac{1}{n},$$

$$(n^*) \sum_{m=0}^k \binom{n}{m} \binom{k}{m} = 2^{n-k} \binom{k}{n}.$$

Yechim. Taqdimotning qisqaligi uchun biz dalillarda faqat algebraik mulohazalardan foydalanamiz.

(a), (b), (c), (j), (l), (a*), (c*), (e*) munosabatlari bevosita tekshirish orqali o'rnatiladi. Tenglik (d),

(f), (f*) kengayish $(x + y)^n$ dan turli xil tanlash x va y usullari ostida kelib chiqadi. Tenglikning

(g), (i) ikkala qismi mos ravishda teng $\frac{d}{dx} (1+x)^n \Big|_{x=1}$ va $\frac{d}{dx} (1+x)^n \Big|_{x=1}$. Bundan tashqari,

munosabatlar (b*), (e), (h*) kengayishlarda mos ravishda x^n uchun k koeffitsientlarining tengligi sifatida $\binom{n}{k} = \binom{n-k}{n-k}$, xossasini hisobga olgan holda olinadi.

$$(1+x)^{n_1} (1+x)^{n_2} = (1+x)^{n_1+n_2},$$

$$(1+x)^n (1+x)^n = (1+x)^{2n},$$

$$(x-1)^n (x+1)^n = (x^2-1)^n.$$

(h) Paskalning taqsimotidan $\binom{k}{n} = \binom{k}{n-1} + \binom{k-1}{n-1}$, ni olamiz, bu

$$\binom{k}{n} - \binom{k-1}{n} + \binom{k-2}{n} - \dots + (-1)^k = \binom{k}{n-1} + \binom{k-1}{n-1} - \binom{k-1}{n-1} - \binom{k-2}{n-1} + \binom{k-3}{n-1} - \dots = \binom{k}{n-1}.$$

ekanligini bildiradi.

(k) Paskal taqsimotidan va xossasidan foydalanib $\binom{k}{k} = \binom{k+1}{k+1}$, ni topamiz

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{k+1}{k+1} + \binom{k}{k+1} + \binom{k}{k+2} + \dots + \binom{k}{n} &= \binom{k+1}{k+2} + \binom{k}{k+2} + \dots + \binom{k}{n} = \\ &= \binom{k+1}{k+3} + \binom{k}{k+2} + \dots + \binom{k}{n} = \binom{k+1}{n+1}. \end{aligned}$$

(m) tenglik koeffitsientlarning tengligidan kelib chiqadi. x^n ning kengaytmalarida

$$\sum_{m=0}^k \binom{k}{m} (1+x)^{m+n} = \frac{1}{x} \frac{d}{dx} (1+x)^{n+k+1} - (1+x)^n \frac{d}{dx}$$

(n) $\sum_{m=0}^k \binom{k}{m} C_{n+1}^m = 2^{n+1} - \sum_{m=0}^{n-k} \binom{n-k}{m} C_{n+1}^m$ ekanligini unutmang. Istalgan xususiyat kengayishida x^{n-k}

uchun koeffitsientlarning tengligi quyidagicha

$$(1 + x + x^2 + \dots)(2^{n+1} - (1 + x)^{n+1}) = \frac{2^{n+1} - (1 + x)^{n+1}}{1 - x} = \sum_{m=0}^n (1 + x)^{n-m} 2^m.$$

(d*) Bizda

$$C_{m+n}^m = \frac{(m+n)!}{m!n!} = \frac{m!}{n!} + \frac{m}{n} \frac{m-1}{n-1} + \frac{m(m-1)}{n(n-1)} + \dots + \frac{m(m-1)\dots(m-k+1)}{n(n-1)\dots(n-k+1)} + \dots + \frac{m(m-1)\dots(m-n+1)}{n(n-1)\dots(n-n+1)}$$

bor.

(i*) $\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k (C_n^k)^3$ qiymat kengayishidagi $x^n y^n z^n$ koeffitsientiga ajraladi

$$(x - y)^n (y - z)^n (z - x)^n$$

$(x - y)^{n-1} (y - z)^{n-1} (z - x)^{n-1}$ ko'phad toq n uchun simmetrikdir, demak $(x - y)(y - z)(z - x) = x^2z - x^2y + y^2x - y^2z + z^2y - z^2x$, dagi koeffitsient $x^n y^n z^n$ nolga teng degan xulosaga kelish oson.

Endi n teng bo'lsin. Keling uni qo'yamiz

$$C_x^k = \frac{x(x-1)\dots(x-k+1)}{k!}.$$

$2n$ darajali ko'phadlarning quyidagi tengligini isbotlaymiz:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{2n} (-1)^k C_{2n}^k C_x^k C_x^{2n-k} = (-1)^n C_x^n C_{x+n}^n.$$

$x = 0, 1, \dots, n - 1$ da ikkala tomon ham nolga teng, chunki $C_x^n = 0$ va $C_x^k = 0$ yoki $C_x^{2n-k} = 0$. $x = n$ da birinchi ko'phad ikkinchi ko'phadning $x = n$ nuqtasidagi qiymatiga teng nolga teng bo'lmagan bitta hadga ega bo'ladi. $x = -n, -n + 1, \dots$ bizda $C_{x+n}^n = 0$ bor

$$f(k) = C_x^k C_x^{2n-k} = C_{|x|+k-1}^k C_{|x|+2n-k-1}^{n-k} = C_{|x|+k-1}^{|x|-1} C_{|x|+2n-k-1}^{|x|-1}$$

funksiya esa k (darajalari $2|x| - 2 < 2n$), da ko'phad, shuning uchun (k*) xossasidan kelib chiqib, quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz.

$$\sum_{k=0}^{2n} (-1)^k C_{2n}^k f(k) = 0.$$

Shunday qilib, $2n$ darajali ko'phadlar $2n + 1$ nuqtaga to'g'ri keldi, shuning uchun

ular bir-biriga teng. $x = 2n$ o'rnatib, biz Diksonning taqsimotini olamiz hatto n uchun ham.

(g*) va (n*) munosabatlar x uchun koeffitsientlarning tengligidir x^{n-k} mos ravishda kengayishlarda

$$(1+x)^n = \sum_{m=0}^n C_n^m (1+2x)^m (-x)^{n-m}$$

va

$$(1+2x)^n = \sum_{m=0}^n C_n^m (1+x)^m x^{n-m}.$$

(j*) Bizda

$$\sum_{k=1}^n C_n^k \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{k} = \int_0^1 \frac{1-(1-x)^n}{x} dx = \int_0^1 (1+(1-x) + \dots + (1-x)^{n-1}) dx = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k}.$$

bor

(k*) $f_0(1)$ qiymati $m = 0$ da kerakli summani hosil qiladi, bunda $f_0(x) = (x-1)^n$.

$f_m(x)$ ni rekursiy aniqlaymiz: $f_m(x) = x f'_{m-1}(x)$. Keyin $f_m(1) = 0$ va $m \leq n$ uchun kerakli summa. Bu yerdan xulosa qilish oson. $f_m(1) = 0$ uchun $m < n$ va $f_n(1) = n!$

(l*) Tenglik $f(x) = \sum_{n^3 0} C_{2n}^n x^n$ da $f(x)^2 = \frac{1}{1-4x} = \sum_{n^3 0} 2^{2n} x^n$ ga teng.

Ikkinchisi $f(x) = (1-4x)^{-1/2}$ tenglikdan kelib chiqadi, funksiyani kengaytirish orqali tekshirish oson $(1-4x)^{-1/2}$ tenglikdagi Teylor qatori $x = 0$ nuqta.

(m*) Da

$$\sum_{m=1}^k \frac{1}{m} = \int_0^1 (1+x + \dots + x^{k-1}) dx = \int_0^1 \frac{1-x^k}{1-x} dx$$

dan boshlab quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{k-1} C_n^k \sum_{m=1}^k \frac{1}{m} = \int_0^1 \frac{1+(1-x)^n - 1}{1-x} dx = \frac{1}{n}.$$

Mustaqil yechish uchun masalalar

№ 1. (n) (Арнольд) C_n^k ekanligini isbotlang, agar k va n o'zaro teng bo'lsa, n ga bo'linadi ($k < n$).

(m) p tub son bo'lsin. $C_{2p}^p \equiv 2 \pmod{p}$ ni ko'rsating.

№ 2. N sonining bo'limlari soni ko'pi bilan ikkita ekanligini ko'rsating, $\sum_{d|N} \frac{1}{d} \equiv 1 \pmod{N}$ ga teng, bu erda $\sum_{d|N} \frac{1}{d}$ x sonining butun qismi.

№ 3. Ikkinchi turdagi Stirling raqami S_N^n ta elementlar to'plamining mumkin bo'lgan qismlari soni sifatida aniqlanadi, aytaylik $\{1, 2, \dots, N\}$, N ta bo'sh bo'lmagan kichik to'plamlarga ega.

1 $\leq n \leq N$ da quyidagi xususiyatlar mavjudligini ko'rsating:

$$(a) S_N^1 = S_N^N = 1, S_N^2 = 2^{N-1} - 1, S_N^{N-1} = C_N^2;$$

$$(b) S_{N+1}^n = S_N^{n-1} + nS_N^n;$$

$$(c) S_{N+1}^n = \sum_{k=0}^N C_N^k S_k^{n-1} \left(S_k^p = 0 \text{ agar } p > k \right);$$

$$(d) S_N^n = \frac{1}{n!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{n-k} C_n^k k^N;$$

$$(e) S_N^n = \frac{1}{n!} \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k C_n^k (n-k)^N;$$

$$(f) S_N^n \leq n^{N-n} C_{N-1}^{n-1}.$$

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR.

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